

Athens Sandbox: EcoTechWall, SmartWall and Nest Control Installation

The GreeNest project is pleased to announce the completion of the installation of four advanced façade and control components at its **Athens Sandbox** demo site on the campus of [National Technical University of Athens \(NTUA\)](#). These include three variants of the EcoTechWall envelope system, the SmartWall modular façade system, and the NestControl digital monitoring and operational system. The performance monitoring campaign for all four components has started in January 2026.

Installation at the Athens Sandbox

The Athens Sandbox serves as a experimental space where next-generation building systems can be installed, swapped and tested combining fully controlled indoor conditions with real outdoor weather exposure. The Athens Sandbox is designed for rapid and simplified installation thanks to its **prefabricated cargotecture structure** (steel load-bearing frame reusing two shipping containers) and **detachable façade elements** that allow components to be swapped with minimal effort. Its modular masonry panels, plug and play energy systems and reversible connections make the building an ideal testbed where new walls, windows and active systems can be easily installed or removed within hours rather than days. This flexibility speeds up experimentation and reduces downtime, allowing **rapid validation** of multiple technologies in **real conditions**.

NTUA Sandbox with detachable façade elements

Installation of GreeNest components

NTUA Sandbox with GreeNest walls

In GreeNest, the Athens Sandbox is used to demonstrate the operational performance of the **17 Standardised Packages** of the project: **innovative envelope systems** (the EcoTechWall and the SmartWall), **low embodied carbon materials** (Light clay and KARZ), **active systems** (CASCADE HVAC system, EV charger, PVs), **advanced windows** (Heat Harvest Windows) and **control system** (NestControl), all monitored through a unified digital environment.

The Athens Sandbox operates as a **Living Lab**, engaging stakeholders like students, researchers, architects and engineers, and providing transparent access to the evolution of innovative components for **zero emission building** (GreeNest ecosystem). This Living Lab offers a rare combination of real-scale testing, flexible reconfiguration and full sensor-based evaluation, creating a powerful platform for validating low carbon materials, intelligent controls and integrated design approaches before deployment in large European demo sites.

The **EcoTechWall**, one of the Standardised Packages, is a low embodied carbon wall system that emphasizes circular-economy using biogenic and recycled materials. At the Athens Sandbox, **three variants** of the EcoTechWall envelope were installed in October 2025, representing different material or assembly strategies to enable comparative performance monitoring:

1. **EcoTechWall North European type (NEU1):** adapted for North European climatic conditions and constructed using **recycled wood, wood fibre and cellulose insulation**, acting as the control setup.
2. **EcoTechWall North European type (NEU2):** adapted for North European climatic conditions and constructed using **recycled wood and KARZ insulation**, combining waste coffee grounds and polyurethane.
3. **EcoTechWall South European type (SEU):** adapted for South European climatic conditions to address Athens cooling-dominated needs and local material availability, incorporating **light clay bricks** combining clay with straw; it is demonstrated for the first time.

Wood fibre insulation

KARZ insulation

Light clay bricks

The **SmartWall**, another GreeNest Standardised Package, is a modular, prefabricated façade wall system combining low-embodied-carbon materials with embedded active fire protection system and indoor environmental quality control system. The installation of the SmartWall at the Athens sandbox allows real-world testing of its ability to achieve near-zero energy building (NZEB) status through high insulation (U-value as low as 0.16 W/m²K) and integrated services.

SmartWall

The **NestControl system** is the digital and IoT component of the GreenNest ecosystem, enabling monitoring, control and data collection for envelope performance, indoor environment and energy use. At the Athens Sandbox the NestControl architecture has been deployed alongside the façade systems to capture real-time data streams once the performance phase begins.

Monitoring Phase

Starting January 2026, a detailed performance monitoring campaign will commence covering all four façade components. Key parameters will include thermal insulation performance, operational energy consumption, indoor environmental quality (via thermal and visual comfort conditions and indoor air quality metrics), and durability/maintenance indicators. The comparative data from the three EcoTechWall variants will enable robust analysis of how different material approaches perform under Mediterranean climate conditions. The EcoTechWall, SmartWall and NestControl system will provide a holistic envelope, services, monitoring data set. The results will feed into GreenNest's digital tools, replication guidelines and standardisation efforts ([bimetica.com](https://www.bimetica.com)).

Significance

By installing multiple façade system variants on a live test-bed in Athens, the [GreenNest project](#) enables region-specific validation of advanced envelope technologies and digital monitoring. The hybrid of nature-based/recycled materials with smart modular design and building services is aligned with EU objectives of 100 % carbon-free construction and near-zero energy buildings. The Athens Sandbox thus becomes a showcase and knowledge hub for architects, engineers, material developers and building owners seeking high-performance, low-carbon façades.

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